

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 6; June 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

This issue of J.UCS, a special issue on Distance Teaching, was edited by Professor Bernd Krämer from the University of Hagen, Germany. Bernd Krämer is one of the key computer scientists in Germany involved in distance teaching and involved in a variety of European projects in this area. I am very pleased that he was willing to select the best papers of a symposium that he organized.

I am sure that many of you will enjoy reading the papers! Note that after two special issues (May and June 96) we will return to "ordinary" issues for the next few months: however, it is a pleasure to report that further special issues on the WWW, on CSCW and on Security are also in preparation!

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu